

Local Government in Spain

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Francisco Velasco Caballero, Silvia Díez Sastre, Ester Marco Peñas,
Mónica Domínguez Martín, Alfonso Egea de Haro and Carmen Navarro Gómez

Instituto de Derecho Local
Universidad Autónoma de Madrid

Partners

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism

University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

ximpulse
Ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

Faculty of Political Science
and International Studies
University of Warsaw
University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

UNIVERSIDAD
NACIONAL DE
SAN MARTÍN

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

जवाहरलाल नेहरू विश्वविद्यालय
Jawaharlal Nehru University

Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University
of Singapore
National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

UNIVERSITY · CANADA
University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Spain is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero, Silvia Díez Sastre, Ester Marco Peñas, Mónica Domínguez Martín, Alfonso Egea de Haro, Carmen Navarro Gómez
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malfertheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Steven Yu/Pixabay

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Spain	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Spain: An Introduction	6
2.2. <i>Digitalization of Rural Areas in Castilla y León</i>	8
2.3. <i>Tragsa as an Instrument of Providing Essential Services in Rural Areas</i>	12
2.4. <i>Nursing Homes for the Elderly</i>	16
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Spain: An Introduction	21
3.2. <i>Financing Rural Local Governments Faced with Depopulation, Ageing and Dispersion</i>	24
3.3. <i>The Local Recovery Plan to Overcome the Effects of Covid-19</i>	27
3.4. <i>Delegation of Tax Competences to Upper-Tier Local Bodies: The Case of OAPs</i>	30
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Spain: An Introduction	35
4.2. <i>The Role of Provinces for the Provision of Services by Small Rural Local Governments</i>	38
4.3. <i>The Counties (comarcas) in Aragon and Catalonia</i>	41
4.4. <i>Exploring Sub-Municipal Units of Government in Rural Local Governments</i>	44
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Spain: An Introduction	49
5.2. <i>The Coordinating Role of Local Government Associations in Intergovernmental Relations: The Case of FEMP</i>	51
5.3. <i>Regional Plans to Prevent Depopulation of Rural Areas</i>	58
5.4. <i>The Basque Council for Local Public Policies</i>	63
6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Spain: An Introduction	69
6.2. <i>Participatory Budgeting in 'Decide Madrid'</i>	72
6.3. <i>The Experience of 'Local Action Groups' as Quality Participation in Rural Areas</i>	75
6.4. <i>Promoting Public Participation in Urban Planning Processes as a Bottom-up Process: Urban-Rural Differences</i>	80

Local Financial Arrangements

3.2. Financing Rural Local Governments Faced with Depopulation, Ageing and Dispersion

Francisco Velasco Caballero (coord), Félix D. Laguna Martínez, César Martínez Sánchez, Félix Vega Borrego, Diego Marín-Barnuevo Fabo, Ester Marco Peñas, *Instituto de Derecho Local, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid*

Relevance of the Practice

Rural areas face three enormous demographic challenges nowadays: depopulation, ageing and dispersion. These three factors impact negatively on municipal budgets. On the one hand, depopulation and ageing reduce tax revenue as they usually imply an economic downturn. On the other hand, the dispersion of population typical of rural areas, added to the increasing depopulation and ageing of several central regions of the country, may (and do) increase the cost of providing public services.

Description of the Practice

Having this in mind, the relevant practice relates to the insufficient attention paid to specific demographic issues (e.g. depopulation, dispersion and ageing) by the state within its financial transfer scheme. This reality lead to the undercompensation –if any– of the existing differences between large Spanish municipalities, which increase in population, and small and medium municipalities, which otherwise age and decrease in population.

Moreover, the unequal treatment of large and small (and medium) municipalities related to the already mentioned disregarded factors of depopulation, ageing and dispersion might even worsen taking into account the participation (approx. 2 per cent) of large municipalities (98) on state tax revenue collected in each large city (e.g. VAT and Personal Income Tax). This extraordinary revenue is based on three variables: total population of each city (75 per cent), average tax effort (12.5 per cent) and the inverse of the ability to pay or fiscal capacity (12.5 per cent). Theoretically, whereas the last variable refers to the broadness of tax bases, the second one refers to the tax rate set by each municipality. Small Spanish municipalities (8,026) do not receive these extraordinary revenues and this might exacerbate the unbalancing effects of the insufficient recognition of dispersion and ageing in the implementation of the general financial transfer scheme.

Assessment of the Practice

Under the Spanish legislation, local governments are required to provide certain services according to their size. Therefore, the main purpose of the financing system is to assign sufficient financial resources to local governments so that they may comply with that obligation.

However, insufficient recognition of depopulation dispersion and ageing within the financial transfer scheme might allow considering that the general financial system does not aim at an actual leveling between local governments. Indeed, it can exacerbate the divide between rural and urban areas. The following provisional conclusions could be drawn from recent empirical studies:

- cities of more than 500,000 inhabitants are *over*-financed (due to the status quo clause);
- there are enormous – and unjustified – *differences* regarding per capita financing (e.g., Barcelona receives EUR 701 per inhabitant, while Almeria receives EUR 227);
- unlike the financing system for autonomous communities, the current local government financing system does not address the main problems of rural municipalities: population decrease, ageing and dispersion;
- the system does *not* take into account the effective costs of service provision either, which may adversely affect rural municipalities, where public services are more expensive (due to the lack of diseconomies of scale).

Notwithstanding this assessment, it must also be taken into account that the second tier of local government (the provinces) is obliged by the laws to provide the municipalities with financial and technical assistance, what partially rebalances the comparative underfunding of small -and mainly rural- local governments.

The workshops and interviews conducted for this ‘relevant practice’ show that the current local financing scheme ensures the provision of mandatory local services (water supply, sewerage, maintenance of public roads, etc.). In relation to this general conclusion, three important clarifications are necessary.

First, although demographic aging naturally results in a higher cost of public health and care services, this phenomenon does not necessarily produce an imbalance in local financing, since the provision of those services corresponds mainly to the autonomous communities, not to the municipalities.

Second, rural inhabitants do not receive any favorable treatment from the local financial system. Although the fiscal capacity of small municipalities is normally smaller than that of large municipalities (due to lower wealth rates and less economic activity), public services in small municipalities are also largely financed by local taxes. Consequently, the local *tax burden*

on the inhabitants of rural areas is very similar to that of the inhabitants of urban municipalities.

Third, the rural neutrality of the local financial system is partially offset by the technical and financial assistance and cooperation of the provinces (second tier of local government). However, this compensatory effect is very different among the 50 provinces. The workshops and interviews carried out in this relevant practice show that some provinces concentrate all their economic and personal resources in rural municipalities (as it is the case of Valladolid), while other provinces (such as Barcelona) allocate a significant part of their income to urban municipalities, so that rebalancing effect with regard to rurality is less relevant.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Bosch Roca N and Suárez Pandiello J, 'Politics and Finance in Spanish Municipalities' (2015) 212 Hacienda pública Española 51

Echániz Sans J, 'Los Gobiernos locales después de la crisis. Un Análisis de las Haciendas Locales en el período 2001-2016' (Fundación Democracia y Gobierno Local 2019)

Ministry of Finance, 'Publicación de los de los Presupuestos de las Entidades Locales' (2021) <<https://www.hacienda.gob.es/es-ES/Areas%20Tematicas/Administracion%20Electronica/OVEELL/Paginas/PublicacionPresupuestosEELL.aspx>>

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

